

Desk Review of Impact of Coronavirus on the Aviation Sector in the United States

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Abstract

Desk review in this context is an assessment of global pandemic event of COVID-19 and Omicron specifically as it concerns United States of America. The purpose of this research is to determine the impact of COVID-19 on aviation sector of United States. This is with a view to assess pattern of passengers' movement and employees' employment status after the pandemic in the United States' air transport industry. Downloaded research articles and data from Bureau of Transportation Statistics - United States Department of Transportation were analyzed with descriptive statistics of tables, graphs and histogram. Apart from recorded loss of lives and restriction of movements, demand for air travel and tourism was greatly affected by the pandemic. There was a steady increase in passenger movement by air across South America, Central America, Canada and North America regions of United States. It could be observed that, North America demands for air travel during and a bit after COVID-19 was above all regions followed by Canada with a steady observation for about six months before rise in travel demand. Full time employees recorded in the airline from 2010 to 2022 on monthly basis have not been matched since the pandemic especially from October to December. While acknowledging the roles played by Centre for Diseases Control and World Health Organization to contain the pandemic, their recommendations from history must be followed by all stakeholders in future.

Introduction

The purpose of this research is to determine the impact of COVID-19 on aviation sector of United States. This is with a view to assess pattern of passengers' movement and employees' employment status after the pandemic in the United States' air transport industry. Air transport is very crucial for national, international, economic, health and other urgent transactions. The outbreak of Coronavirus pandemic was said to emanate from Wuhan in China. According to Adepoju China informed World Health Organization of a global pandemic which attacks lungs and cause problems in breathing which may eventually lead to the death of its host [1]. Lu, et al expressed that, over 44 million confirmed cases had been reported as at October 5, 2021 in the United States [2]. The Centre for Disease Control noted that over 720,000 deaths had been

recorded [3]. The closure of borders, airports and all economic activities as a result of lockdown all over the world could not make anyone demand for air transport. Restrictions by countries on the control for the pandemic put a halt on tourism, international and local air travels. Though many reports from Centre for Disease Control could not confirm that Coronavirus is an airborne infection but, the investigations from CDC observed that, while a woman was traveling by air from London to Vietnam, she infected 15 other passengers prior to the period of face mask mandate on the 10 hours journey. Due to the fact that, international flights in particular which is prominent in United States used to be effected through interconnection of different people from different parts of the world, it was presumed to be an agent of spread of coronavirus. IATA predicted that, the hit of coronavirus and omicron on

More Information

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aviation sector in the United States reduced the travel by air by 60% in 2020 and the industry may fully recover in 2024 [4]. The worst is the predictions of variants of the virus with omicron variant recently. The economic effect of coronavirus and omicron in the aviation sector of United States can be seen in form of low or no production of aircraft, less demand for tourism and recreation, reduction in tax revenue as a major source of income for Airport and Airway Trust Fund (AATF) which it uses include financial aids, grants and some other developmental projects. About 100,000 aerospace manufacturing workers lost their jobs because of COVID-19 and many more were probably forced to take half of their salaries [5]. One of the imbalances of the economy brought by coronavirus was the initiative of government to divert funds meant for other programmes to salvage situations in the aviation industry. For instance, Payroll Support Programme (PSP) was a programme initiated with about \$32 billion for airlines to preserve the jobs of their employees. This fund was accessed in the course of finding solutions to the pandemic. Reviewing impact of COVID-19 on the aviation sector of United States can serve as a guide to cushion future occurrence and tame the dimensions of its effects on global affairs.

Review of relevant Literatures on COVID-19 and Omicron in the U.S

Conspiracy theory and Spread of COVID-19

The perception and various reports on coronavirus pandemic came with disbeliefs because of different notions as the virus could not be detected until large number of persons were being taken to different hospitals. It was almost immediately the report of SARS-CoV-2 virus was announced, the virus responsible for COVID-19, World Health Organization and Centre for Disease Control swung into action to tame the virus. As many people in different parts of the world did not know what was going on, fake news and spread of conspiracy theories and general mass suspicion clouded the year 2019 and early 2020 on COVID-19. Vincent described a situation where people assumed COVID-19 was caused by 5G cellular technology or that Bill Gates intended to force vaccination on people for enslavement and surveillance purposes [6]. The Director General of World Health organization had to confess that *“we are not only fighting pandemic, we are also fighting infodemic* [7]. There is a change in transmission of information as there is an unprecedented impact of how it is produced, transmitted and consumed [7]. Social medial platforms like Twitter, Facebook, Whatsapp and other digital technologies are avenue for sharing fake news that gullible will quickly consume and redistribute them. The outbreak of Ebola virus was discovered in West Africa in 2014 and scientists were able to discover its vaccine after about five years. It was the awareness of

this virus that necessitated GAO to make recommendations that United States Department of Transportation in conjunction with department of Heal Services should develop a preparedness plan against types of communicable diseases threats. It was reported by the committee on Aviation on COVID-19 that, Department of Transportation did not execute the plan which would have assisted in the fight against COVID-19. Humayum noted that airline passengers were subjected to pre-flight test “Safe Travel Corridors” to ascertain destination country’s sanctions and quarantine requirements [10].

Cargo and passenger airlines in United States employed up to 750,000 workers [9]. More than half of these population lost their jobs in aviation industry as a result of COVID-19. In order to contain the pandemic, people were admonished to wear face mask so as to prevent them from contacting it and at the same time from spreading the disease by those who have contacted it already. All personnel working directly with airlines like, pilot, flight attendants, gateman, service workers and security agents were at risk of contacting the viruses. This is due to the fact that passengers most times refuse to keep to the rules of using face mask and social distancing precautions. Executive Order by President Biden mandated face mask must be worn in all modes of transportation and at the terminus. Laris noted that, flight attendants receive all kinds of insults while trying to enforce precautions against the spread of the virus [10]. Many passengers opined that, face mask cannot be worn for long hours and there were periods they need to drink or eat. There were penalties from warning to payment of fines and serving jail terms for violating COVID-precautionary measures [11]. Total lockdown was declared and Centre for Disease Control was mandated to commence contact tracing, create isolation centres and ensure movement restrictions of victims of COVID-19. United States Food and Drug Administration permitted the use of Moderna and Pfizer- BioNTech COVID-19 vaccines as emergency use authorization vaccines for persons above 16 years of age. Thereafter, in 2021 around February, Johnson and Johnson vaccine was approved for emergency use by the Food and Drug Administration having met certain criteria [12].

An historic shift is being witnessed in U.S aviation industry with the growth recorded in the areas of Unmanned Aircrafts, electric aircrafts and emergence of new entrants to cushion congestion, effect of COVID-19 and movement at lower altitude across regions in the industry.

Lu et al examined the perception of passengers of air transport and concluded that, they have adapted to the new normal [2]. Maneenop and Kotcharin found out that airline stocks have declined after examining 52 airlines in United States [13]. Lacus et al. in their studies

focused on the trend of GDP of United States and concluded that, there is decline in global Gross Domestic Product (GDP) by 0.02- 0.12% [14]. Jiang [15] and Albers et al. [16] found out that, short distance hauls are more profitable with less restrictions compared with long hauls during the heat of the pandemic. Usually the short hauls are low cost services with economy and conditions of no free meal and maximum utilization of aircraft. According to O’Connell full service airline used to provide in-flight meals, personalized services and supporting facilities [15]. In the study conducted by Kókény et al, it was found that; different airlines were affected differently by COVID-19 among the selected European airlines using stock market performance [16]. ICAO observed a trend of analysis of pandemic since 1945 to 2020 and observed that impact of COVID-19 was unprecedented in the history [17]. In the study of Lu, Zhu, Li, Liang and Zhang Alaska Airlines, Delta Air Lines, United Airlines, and Hawaiian Airlines, American Airlines were classified as full-service airlines and JetBlue Airways, Southwest Airlines, Allegiance Airlines, Spirit Airlines, Ryanair were considered as low-cost airlines [2]. Generally their results revealed that there is now reduction in risk perception of passengers across all the airlines. Two major factors were enumerated to be agents of the risk reduction. First, is the various preventive measures by the industry and secondly, passengers have adapted to the new conditions of travel and have experienced a moderate level of recovery. Carriage of half capacity during COVID and Omicron reduces the revenue generated by the airlines. Again, it was asserted that, the direct and indirect economic impacts of airports for its propensities to generate development were stalled by COVID-19 and Omicron viruses.

Asian Development Bank conducted an assessment of the impact of COVID-19 on tourism of 10 countries of Central Asian Region Economic Cooperation (CAREC) comprising Afghanistan, Mongolia, Uzbekistan, Tajikistan, Pakistan, Georgia, Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan and the Kyrgyz Republic [18]. It was observed that, international, domestic and regional flights across CAREC countries were down by over 90% in 2020. The assessment impact noted that, \$7 billion revenue was lost to the pandemic by CAREC in 2020. Also, it has impact on the visitors of 33 million; all allied aviation jobs of about 25,000 in tourism were brought to a halt because of COVID-19 [19]. Flights on religious services emanating from countries all over the world could not be generated because of COVID-19. Georgia in particular is dependent mostly on inbound traffic of visitors whose passage influences accommodation revenue, tourism, local markets, beverages, food and other human needs essentials. Liu et al were able to explain the extent of liquidity in airline industry arising from COVID-19 pandemic with the use of Generalized

Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) model [20]. In the stocks and financial markets, aviation industry can only gradually recover the loss in years to come of what the pandemic has eroded. Elias reported that, the measure to curtail COVID-19 started in United States by restricting passengers from China then from Iran, Europe and Brazil [20]. Similarly, European Union placed restrictions on United States but later eased the movement restrictions. The return of air travel in July 2020 witnessed an increase from previous 2019 with about 700,000 passenger daily traffic as against 2,6 million daily passengers before COVID-19 [20]. In the study conducted by IATA it was found out that majority of air passenger travelers said that they will wait for 6 to 12 months before returning to air travel [21]. In Figure 1 U.S Department of Transportation provided a descriptive statistics of work from home in aviation sector from 2019 to 2021.

Figure 1: Work from home statistics
Source: [23]

COVID-19 pandemic is the first to hit jet air travel most in history as against influenza pandemic of 1918 because it least affected aviation as there was no more use of aviation industry as today [22]. Influenza pandemic caused over 1 million deaths all over the world and more than 100 thousand in United States. Markings of airport floors to ensure social distancing was highly promoted and leaving a seat inside the plane between passengers. While airlines argue that, leaving of space is not economical and definitely will affect load factor. Sixteen quarantine centers at the entry of United States’ major airports including other four at other places were set up for quarantine, contact tracing for the purpose of identifying contagious passengers of the disease. Once a passenger has identified of the disease, the contact tracing of the persons who has been infected began. The persons are put in isolation for certain period of time and in some certain cases they may be asked to be self-quarantined. U.S has the legal authority to deny anyone who wants to enter her airport with symptoms or suspected to have contacted a virus. A temperature check is the first thing used in

detecting people with the virus. Another approach used to contain the virus was to decontaminate affected areas. Most aircrafts at the time were dis-infected with the use of chemical to fumigate and kill any virus in the aircraft, lavatories and cabin.

Methodology

This study assessed the impact of COVID-19 on air travel in United States. At random, many papers and online reports authenticated by Centre for Disease control facts were downloaded with a view to understanding the impacts. Out of 73 reports on U.S COVID-19 about 55 (76%) were captured to have adequately and accurately detailed the events of the pandemic. Secondly, data were generated from Airlines for America and the Department of Transportation, United States websites for the purpose of employees' data in U.S airlines and International Civil Aviation Organization.

Results and Discussion

Investigating the results from collected data from Airlines for America 2023, as shown in Figure 2, the interval between years 2018-2022 was the least carried of passengers by all airlines operating in United States because of the pandemic. Over the years, a steady increase in number of passengers has been maintained since 1978.

Figure 2: Travel by Air in United States from 1978-2022 Statistics

Table 1 (Appendix 1) shows the monthly statistics of U.S Travellers in 2021. It can be observed from the above data that Table 1 (Appendix 1) that on monthly basis, in the year 2021 the travel statistics keeps increasing and got highest at each month in December across the regions in South America, Central America, Canada and North America. The analysis for Table 1 is better described by Figure 3 with movements of travellers in United States across four regions of United States i.e South America, Central America, Canada and North America.

Figure 3: Travel by Air in United States in year 2021

The indication from Figure 3 revealed that, passenger travel by air occurred more in North America than all other regions in United States during the post declaration of COVID-19 in the year 2021 across all the months. Noticeably, there is steady increase across the region as we move from one month to another; Canada region tend to observe the trend of events for about six months before passengers could have confidence to increase their movements. However, it may partly be as

a result of restrictions and lockdown measure to contain the pandemic. Central America was a bit not stable at interval of test running flight with increase in downward movements at relative interval of two months. Similar to Canada, South America progressively increased its passenger flights from January to December. In a way, this analysis suggests the travel demand by regions in United States excluding

measures of enforcement and restrictions placed by passengers at other regions.

Below is the data for North America provided by International Civil Aviation Organization on passenger travel in North America.

Table 2: North America Passenger Traffic 2019-2021

Months	2019	2020	2021
Jan	12789	12381	2662
Feb	11189	10439	1835
Mar	13587	6858	2523
Apr	12181	381	1669
May	13368	351	3305

Jun	14491	630	4236
Jul	15501	1203	5237
Aug	15262	1670	5577
Sep	12630	1317	4692
Oct	12343	1637	5140
Nov	11388	1990	5982
Dec	13163	1750	7340

Source: [17]

The data provided by ICAO has been translated into Figure 4 below. The blue color represents 2019, 2020 and 2021 represent red and green colors respectively.

Figure 4: Chart for 2019 – 2021 passenger traffic in North America
Source: Authors' Analysis (2021)

Figure 4 shows that the year 2019 witnessed steady increase in passenger traffic in North America as part of United States but nosedived around August to November which later picked up gradually by December but unlike the first quarter months. From January 2020 till December of the year, air travel passenger plummeted. This can be seen as the red colour across months retrogressed and only picked and started rising form January of 2021 with slow but steady rise. In the data analyzed by Bureau of Labour Statistics, it was observed that the rate of unemployment increased during the pandemic [9]. This was as a result of downsized and lack of demand for some products which is caused by immobility, precaution of social distancing and isolation.

The unemployment rate as shown in Figure 5 decreased between 2005 and 2010 but started recovering steadily till the advent of pandemic which significantly made unemployment to rise to it pick in 2020.

Figure 5: Unemployment in United States
Source: Authors' analysis (2022)

Table 4 (Appendix 1) presented the full-time employee data in aviation industry of United States of America. Observations between year 2022 and 2023 revealed that there is increase in employment rate as against

what can be observed at the heat of COVID-19 pandemic. In order to have a better view of the years,

2023 was excluded and close observation into full years between 2010 and 2022 is depicted with Figure 6.

Figure 6: Employees per month from 2010- 2022 in Air transport of United States

Examining Figure 6 as the output from Table 4 (Appendix 1) indicated the yet to be balanced industry of aviation as a lot of employees left the industry and till date the vacuum seems not to have been filled. Figure 6 revealed the monthly was badly affected during the month of September to December as a fall out of effect of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The impact of COVID-19 and Omicron viruses cannot be forgotten in the history of mankind. Significantly, lack of movement perpetuated poverty and restrictions brought untold hardships. For aviation industry, the paralysis could be felt by loss of jobs by workers as the various companies could not pay salaries. Apart from recorded loss of lives and restriction of movements, demand for air travel and tourism was greatly affected by the pandemic. There was a steady increase in passenger movement by air across South America, Central America, Canada and North America regions of United States. It could be observed that, North America demands for air travel during and a bit after COVID-19 was above all regions followed by Canada with a steady observation for about six months before rise in travel demand. Full time employees recorded in the airline from 2010 to 2022 on monthly basis has not been matched since the pandemic especially from October to December. While acknowledging the roles played by Centre for Diseases Control and World Health Organization to contain the pandemic, their recommendations from history must be followed by all stakeholders in future.

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Appendix 1

Table 1: US citizens Monthly Statistics of Travel by Air in 2021

Months	Jan	Feb	Marc	April	May	Jun	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec	Total
SA	55,904	53,320	78,555	71,311	79,338	115,700	143,042	127,716	117,476	134,929	170,913	253,205	1,401,409
CA	97,060	100,403	168,655	166,320	206,893	290,410	333,905	233,979	165,257	186,894	250,463	385,098	2,585,337
CAN	26,300	19,247	24,525	26,434	35,889	45,297	108,809	374,418	375,858	342,138	303,209	411,289	2,093,413
NA	1,803,467	1,482,568	2,104,871	2,146,815	2,436,806	2,855,317	3,150,290	2,898,456	2,615,118	2,856,375	2,881,941	3,650,580	30,882,604

Source: [24]

Table 4: Full Time Employee for Scheduled Passenger Airlines in United States

Yr	January	Feb	March	April	May	June	July	August	Septe	Octo	Nov	Dec	Grand Total
2010	379,322	378,555	377,807	376,663	377,515	378,859	378,068	378,425	378,263	379,154	380,171	380,409	4,543,211
2011	381,189	382,109	383,311	384,008	385,302	387,113	387,495	387,028	385,788	386,595	386,555	386,939	4,623,432
2012	386,359	387,236	388,113	387,646	388,462	388,291	388,601	386,871	383,735	382,291	381,080	379,716	4,628,401
2013	380,042	380,414	380,540	380,487	381,372	381,672	381,299	380,486	380,165	381,178	381,224	380,809	4,569,688
2014	381,819	381,985	383,575	384,265	385,619	385,243	386,243	384,478	384,501	384,700	386,912	386,222	4,615,562
2015	386,528	388,976	390,817	393,439	395,621	396,973	396,503	397,007	397,326	399,928	401,280	401,440	4,745,838
2016	402,270	403,917	405,983	407,763	410,338	412,333	413,746	414,242	414,558	415,979	416,046	416,337	4,933,512
2017	417,833	419,762	422,278	423,747	425,656	427,818	428,209	428,455	428,673	430,232	429,946	430,607	5,113,216
2018	429,842	433,696	435,710	437,745	439,711	440,929	444,988	441,171	442,049	442,744	441,511	442,015	5,272,111
2019	441,520	442,778	444,708	446,132	447,945	449,714	449,804	449,461	450,454	452,352	452,429	453,663	5,380,960
2020	456,243	458,229	457,260	426,689	409,016	407,693	413,056	411,343	404,764	366,115	364,471	377,209	4,952,088
2021	388,779	393,115	392,250	391,054	394,368	397,618	404,404	409,847	412,757	415,871	417,018	423,553	4,840,634
2022	429,368	434,913	440,836	446,014	452,286	458,144	460,884	463,516	467,030	470,924	472,861	473,349	5,470,123
2023	477,728	482,271	486,551	490,954	495,081	498,509	501,495	503,587	506,337	-	-	-	4,442,512
total	10,191,745	10,214,325	10,232,647	10,226,068	10,241,887	10,273,837	10,292,237	10,270,804	10,228,751	9,678,419	9,655,953	9,663,678	121,170,348

Source: [25]

